

Uniformal Relational Database Optimization Forms

Mirzakhmet Syzdykov
Satbayev University, Almaty, Kazakhstan
mspmail598@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

According to the present time the normal forms are consequent to the efficient data manipulation, still there's no universal method for solving this problem according to the criteria of data to be small and the modeled solution provides the sufficient normalization of the source data.

NORMALIZATION

The normalization problem is to be presented as the mathematical programming problem within the constraints and the main function as the size of data to be minimized.

Earlier we have shown [1] that the factorial number of possible data in each table depends on the number of columns and number of rows. This fact makes it possible to seed the data and store them in a fast and efficient way.

CONCLUSION

As the much earlier works were towards the static structure of the database, for now we have defined the universal approach towards data normalization.

REFERENCES

1. Syzdykov, Mirzakhmet. "Internal Workload of NoSQL Relational Database." *Advanced Technologies and computer science* 2 (2022): 4-7.